

Standard Operating Protocol for the Determination of Ease of Dough Formation of Wet *Fufu* Mash

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SOP: Determination of Ease of Dough Formation of Wet *Fufu* Mash

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ABSTRACT

Fufu is a popular traditional fermented wet paste food product produced from cassava and is widely consumed in Nigeria and other West African countries. Ease of dough formation of wet *fufu* mash during cooking into ready-to-eat dough is one of the key traits that drives acceptance and adoption of cassava varieties by end-users. This SOP is aimed at determining ease of dough formation of wet *fufu* mash from different cassava varieties using champion processors and Rapid Visco-Analyzer (RVA). A scale of 1-5, was employed by champion processors for this evaluation, where 1 signifies slowest and 5, easiest and fastest in dough formation. Other parameters noted were pasting time, temperature, total cooking duration and weight of cooked dough. Pasting properties of the wet *fufu* mash were also obtained using RVA. Ease of cooking evaluation by champion processors correlated negatively and significantly ($R^2 = -0.789$) with RVA peak time. This implies that the lower the peak time, the higher the ease of dough formation, hence peak time of wet *fufu* mash could serve as an indicator for ease of dough formation. Identifying cassava varieties that easily form dough will help in reducing drudgery associated with *fufu* processing, save time, cost and enhances acceptance and adoption of such variety by end-users.

Key Words: Fufu, Dough, Pasting properties, Cassava, SOP, End-users

1 SCOPE AND APPLICATION

This study is aimed at developing a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for determining ease of dough formation of wet *fufu* mash produced from different cassava varieties.

1.1 References

Chijioke U. Madu T, Okoye B, Ogunka A.P, Ejechi M, Ofoeze M, Ogbete C, NJoku D, Ewuziem J, Kalu C, Onymauwa N, Ukeje B, Achonwa O, Forsythe L, Fliedel G, Egesi C. (2021). Quality attributes of *fufu* in South-East Nigeria: guide for cassava breeders. *Int J Food Sci Technol.* 56(3):1247-1257.

Bindzi J.M, Guiama V.D, Ndjouenkeu R. (2014). Combined smoking and drying kinetics of retted cassava pulp and effect on the physicochemical and pasting properties of the extracted starch. *Food and Bioprocess Technology* 7(9):2749-2758.

Yildiz O, Yurt B, Basturk A, Toker O.S, Yilmaz M.T, Karaman S, Daglioglu O. (2013). Pasting properties, texture profile and stress-relaxation behaviour of wheat starch/dietary fibre systems. *Food Research International* 53(2013)278-290.

1.2 Definitions

Fufu: A popular traditional fermented wet paste food product from cassava (Ugo *et al*, 2021).

Dough: A mixture that consists essentially of flour or meal and a liquid such as water and is stiff enough to knead or roll.

Pasting temperature: Minimum energy required to initiate rapid absorption of water and swelling of starch granules resulting in increased viscosity and formation of dough (Bindzi *et al*, 2014).

PT: Pasting time

TCT: Total cooking time

WTC: Weight of dough after cooling

EC: Ease of cooking

1.3 Principle

Fufu is widely processed and consumed by households in Western Africa. Cassava varieties vary with respect to rate at which they form dough during *fufu* processing as well as the textural properties of the dough formed. Processing of wet *fufu* mash into ready-to-eat *fufu* dough requires energy and this, introduces drudgery into *fufu* processing. Ease of dough formation is a desirable attribute that drives the acceptance and adoption of cassava variety by *fufu* end-users and it is related to gelatinization and pasting properties of the fermented *fufu* mash (Ugo *et al*, 2021). When wet *fufu* mash is heated, the starch granules swells, resulting in disruption of hydrogen bonds and melting of the crystallites. The resultant effect is the development of viscosity and formation of dough (Ugo *et al*, 2021). Ease of dough formation is favoured by a lower peak time and pasting temperature which results in reduced labour and processing time (Ugo *et al*, 2021).

1.4 Apparatus

- Weighing balance
- Gas cooker as a source of heat
- Stirring stick

- Stainless cooking pot
- Stop watch
- Measuring cylinder
- Rapid Visco Analyzer (Model RVA 4500, Perten Instrument, Australia)

2 PROCEDURE

- 5kg of each cassava variety was processed into wet *fufu* mash following RTBfoods Laboratory Standard Operating Procedure for Sensory Characterization of *fufu* (<https://doi.10.18167/agritrop/00595>).
- The ready-to-eat *fufu* dough was also prepared using RTBfoods Laboratory Standard Operating Procedure for Sensory Characterization of *fufu* (<https://doi.10.18167/agritrop/00595>) as follows:
 - ✓ 400g of wet *fufu* mash was dissolved into a clean stainless pot containing 280mls of tap water.
 - ✓ The content was placed over a camp cooking gas stove and was allowed to pre-heat for 60 seconds.
 - ✓ The mixture was then stirred continuously using a stirring stick until dough was formed and properly cooked. This is indicated by the formation of a creamy-white homogenous dough as described in the SOP for Sensory Characterization of *fufu* (<https://doi.10.18167/agritrop/00595>).
 - ✓ Using a stop watch, different important times were taken and it included; the time cooking started, the pasting time (taken at the point mixture started to gel), and time taken for the *fufu* to be completely cooked into a dough.
 - ✓ The weight of the cooked *fufu* dough was taken before (immediately after cooking at a temperature of about 80°C) and after cooling (room temperature) using a weighing balance
 - ✓ Evaluation of ease of dough formation of the wet *fufu* mash produced from different cassava varieties was carried out using two champion processors.
 - ✓ A scale of 1-5 was used for this evaluation, where 1 signifies the slowest and 5, the easiest and fastest to form dough.

Figure 1: Cooking of wet *fufu* mash paste until dough formation.

- The pasting properties of the wet *fufu* mash were measured using a Rapid Visco Analyzer (Model RVA 4500, Perten Instrument, and Australia) equipped with a 1000 cmg sensitivity cartridge. An

adjusted weight of each mash and volume of water calculated using the dry matter content of each sample was weighed into a dried empty canister. The mixture was thoroughly stirred, and the canister was fitted into the RVA as recommended. The slurry was heated from 50 to 95°C at a rate of 1.5°C/min, held at this temperature for 15 min, then cooled to 50°C. Viscosity profile indices recorded from the pasting profile with the aid of ThermoLine for Windows Software connected to a computer were; peak viscosity, trough, breakdown, final viscosity, setback, peak time, and pasting temperature.

Figure 2: Rapid Visco-Analyser used in evaluating pasting properties of wet *fufu* mash.

3 EXPRESSION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Anova result of ease of dough formation parameters evaluated by champion processors using six cassava genotypes.

Genotypes	Pasting_time (mins)	Ease_of_cooking	Total_cooking_time (secs)	Wt. of dough before cooling (g)	Wt. of dough after Cooling (g)
BABA70	59.00	3.50	232.50	609.50	604.00
TMEB419	59.00	4.00	189.50	592.00	580.90
TMS011412	60.00	4.00	238.50	613.10	602.30
TMS980505	68.00	3.00	198.50	608.9	593.30
TMS011368	68.50	4.00	205.50	627.90	616.10
NWAOCHA	90.00	3.50	225.00	591.30	542.90
LSD(0.05)	39.33ns	0.94*	73.50ns	45.69	71.45*
%CV	22.70	10.00	13.30		4.70

				2.90	
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Table 2: Pasting properties of wet fufu mash from six cassava genotypes obtained using Rapid Visco-analyser(RVA).

Test	Peak 1	Trough 1	Breakdown	Final Viscosity	Setback	Peak Time (mins)	Pasting Temp (°C)
TMS980505	171.00	160.25	10.75	241.80	81.54	6.70	94.60
NWAOCHA	292.17	237.50	54.67	396.17	158.67	6.00	84.83
TMEB419	406.59	320.38	86.21	501.67	181.30	5.83	83.13
TMS011368	94.09	40.92	53.17	91.83	50.92	4.80	82.35
TMS011412	295.17	264.17	31.00	459.29	195.13	6.04	79.90
BABA 70	492.79	277.38	215.42	467.54	190.17	5.00	78.35

Table 3: Correlation table showing relationship between ease of dough parameters evaluated by Champion processors and pasting properties obtained using Rapid Visco-Analyser.

	<i>PT</i>	<i>TCT</i>	<i>WTC</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>Sp</i>	<i>solubility</i>	<i>crude fiber</i>	<i>Bulk Density g/vol</i>
PT	1.000							
TCT	0.074	1.000						
WTC	-0.751	0.064	1.000					
EC	-0.311	0.134	0.266	1.000				
Sp	0.265	-0.003	-0.061	0.135	1.000			
Solubility	-0.314	0.094	0.725	-0.306	-0.365	1.000		
crude fiber	0.058	0.242	0.143	-0.484	-0.386	0.603	1.000	
Bulk Density g/vol	-0.145	-0.088	0.149	0.347	0.171	-0.066	0.388	1.000
Dispersibility	-0.354	0.078	0.060	0.554	-0.422	-0.225	-0.606	-0.442
Wac	-0.281	0.269	0.503	0.042	0.300	0.370	0.583	0.734
free sugar	0.126	-0.210	-0.564	-0.154	-0.382	-0.459	-0.495	-0.682
Starch	-0.192	-0.285	-0.347	-0.282	-0.677	-0.198	-0.136	-0.450
Amylose	-0.157	-0.384	-0.470	0.264	-0.140	-0.763	-0.606	-0.088
Amylopectin	-0.126	0.210	0.564	0.154	0.382	0.459	0.495	0.682
dry matter	0.354	-0.192	-0.240	-0.394	-0.417	0.201	-0.153	-0.818
Moisture	-0.354	0.192	0.240	0.394	0.417	-0.201	0.153	0.818
Peak 1	0.146	0.262	-0.280	0.362	0.667	-0.692	-0.774	-0.272
Trough 1	0.188	0.239	-0.339	0.046	0.761	-0.643	-0.543	-0.179
Breakdown	0.130	0.261	-0.255	0.436	0.621	-0.684	-0.814	-0.289
Final Visc	0.558	0.341	-0.621	0.120	0.680	-0.750	-0.261	0.154

Setback	0.709	0.295	-0.644	0.146	0.267	-0.514	0.181	0.455
Peak Time	0.234	-0.343	-0.048	-0.789	-0.452	0.582	0.663	-0.111
Pasting Temp	-0.176	-0.539	0.384	0.028	-0.387	0.532	0.432	0.452
dm on f. root	-0.224	-0.118	0.073	0.320	-0.828	0.143	-0.060	-0.191
	<i>PT</i>	<i>TCT</i>	<i>WTC</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>Sp</i>	<i>solubility</i>	<i>crude fiber</i>	<i>Bulk Density g/vol</i>

Table 1 shows the result obtained for parameters employed to determine Ease of dough formation evaluated by champion processors using seven contrasting cassava genotypes

Table 2 on the other hand shows the pasting properties obtained using RVA of those contrasting cassava genotypes

Table 3 is a correlation table showing relationship between functional, chemical, pasting properties and ease of dough parameters evaluated by champion processors.

From the correlation analysis, peak time correlates negatively and significantly ($R^2 = -0.789$) with Ease of cooking (EC) evaluation by champion processors. This implies that the lower the peak time, the higher the ease of dough formation. Peak time which reflects the temperature at peak viscosity and shows the duration required for starch granules to swell and rupture (Yildiz *et al*, 2013), could serve as a tool for identifying cassava varieties that can easily form a dough, leading to reduced cooking time and labour. Also there is a positive correlation between Ease of cooking with dispersibility ($R^2 = 0.554$) of the chips. This implies that the higher the dispersibility of the cassava flour, the higher the dough forming ability of the genotype. The study also revealed that weight of dough after cooling (WTC) exhibited a negative and significant correlation with free sugar ($R^2 = -0.564$), final viscosity ($R^2 = -0.621$) and set back ($R^2 = -0.644$) but positive and significant correlation with solubility ($R^2 = 0.725$) from fresh cassava roots. These attributes may also serve as traits that can be used for selecting cassava with good dough forming ability of fufu. Interestingly, there is a negative correlation ($R^2 = -0.539$) between pasting temperature and total cooking time (TCT), which is an expected trend, implying that increased temperature results in reduced cooking time.

FIG 1: PCA Analysis of six cassava genotypes

Fig 1 is a PCA analysis showing clustering of genotypes, cooking parameters and pasting properties. The result showed that there is a relationship existing among the parameters that are clustered together as can be seen with pasting time, ease of cooking ,setback, swelling power, total cooking time, break down and final viscosity in the green cluster. This result further indicate a close relationship between pasting time and ease of cooking.

Therefore, the pasting RVA property; especially Peak time could serve as mid-throughput method for characterizing and selection of cassava varieties with good ease of dough forming abilities.

4 CRITICAL POINTS OR NOTE ON THE PROCEDURE

- There is need to adjust weight and volume of water during sample preparation of wet fufu mash. This is achieved by calculating the dry matter content of wet *fufu* mash being profiled with the RVA.

5 APPENDICES

5.1 Annex 1: Cooking parameters evaluated by champion processors 1 and 2 on seven cassava genotypes

Processor 1									
Genotype	Wt. of sample (g)	Vol. of water (ml)	Starting time (s)	Ending time (s)	Pastin g time (s)	Total cookin g time (s)	Wt. of dough immediat ely after cooking (g)	Wt. of dough after cooling (g)	Ease of cooking
BABA 70	400	280	11:06	11:11	1:06	4.21	625.97	604.83	3
GOVERNO	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NWAOCHA	400	280	10:48	10:51	2:00	3.15	604.59	508.86	3
TMEB419	400	280	11:19	11:23	1:06	3.26	624.39	602.85	4
TMS011368	400	280	12:54	12:57	1:06	3.23	631.12	627.47	4
TMS011412	400	280	12:43	12:47	1:07	3.58	618.03	599.99	4

TMS980505	400	280	11:08	11:11	1.16	3.11	605.84	578.88	3
Processor 2									
BABA70	400	280	1:17	1:20	0.52	3.24	593.03	603.24	4
GOVERNO	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NWAOCHA	400	280	10:52	10:56	1.00	4.15	578.00	576.86	4
TMEB419	400	280	1:34	1:37	0.52	2.53	559.53	559.03	4
TMS011368	400	280	11:53	11:57	1.11	3.28	624.71	604.82	4
TMS011412	400	280	12:43	12:47	0.53	3.59	608.09	604.70	4
TMS980505	400	280	11:37	11:40	1.00	3.26	612.01	607.72	3